

INTEGRATION OF STEAM-GENERATING HEAT PUMPS

The efficient technology for steam requirements up to 200°C

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF A STEAM-GENERATING HEAT PUMPS?

The advantages for your industrial operation are manifold, including:

- Increasing efficiency
- Reduction of the final energy demand
- Reduction of CO₂ emissions
- Savings in operating costs
- A technology that both heats and cools
- Utilisation of renewable electricity for process heat

WHAT ARE THE REQUIREMENTS FOR MY COMPANY?

- ✓ Available heat source (waste heat)
- ✓ Steam requirement up to ~200°C

Further considerations

- Optimum selection of integration points, taking into account the distance between the heat source and the steam feeding point
- Storage in case of high discrepancy between availability of heat source and steam demand
- Operation of the heat pump as constant as possible (few start-up and shut-down processes)
- High number of operating hours (improved economic performance)

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Set up an initial consultation appointment with the NEFI team!

Step 1: Data collection to select promising integration points and identify potential

Step 2: Concept development and determination of the expected heat pump efficiency

Step 3: Ecological and economic evaluation of the project including estimation of the costs for integration infrastructure (e.g. feed water treatment, expansion of electrical connection capacity)

Step 4: Support with manufacturer enquiries

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